

ORIGINAL RESEARCH article

Juvenile psoriatic arthritis patients at Tripoli Children's Hospital

Soad S. Hashad^{1, 2 *}

¹ Tripoli Children's Teaching Hospital, Ministry of Health, Tripoli, Libya

² Department of Pediatrics, Faculty of Medicine, University of Tripoli, Tripoli, Libya

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed

Received: October 01, 2025, Accepted: November 06, 2025, Published online: November 13, 2025

Copyright © 2025. This open-access article is distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

HOW TO CITE THIS

Hashad SS, Alghareeri S. Juvenile psoriatic arthritis patients at Tripoli Children's Hospital.

Mediterr J Med Res. 2025; 2(4): 230-238. [Article number: 28].

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17610647>

Keywords: Children, Juvenile psoriatic arthritis, psoriatic, rheumatic disease

Abstract: Juvenile psoriatic arthritis (JPsA) is a relatively rare condition in childhood, as it represents about 5.0% of the whole Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis (JIA). There are fewer reports describing the characteristics and outcome of patients with JPsA. The purpose of this study is to determine characteristic features, treatment, and patients' outcomes of JPsA among Libyan children and to compare the findings with other populations worldwide. Medical records of all the patients who met the Vancouver criteria (definite or probable) or ILAR criteria for JPsA, and who were followed up at the Pediatric Rheumatology Clinic in Tripoli Children's Hospital between 2001 and 2020, were retrospectively reviewed, and data were analyzed. The study included a total of 12 cases of JPsA over the study period; all were met Vancouver criteria for juvenile PsA: 42.0% not fulfill ILAR criteria. JPsA represents 4.8% of total JIA cases with a male-to-female ratio of 1: 1, and a mean age of 10.2±6.5 years. The mean age of disease onset was 5.8±5.3 years. Polyarticular pattern was the predominant (58.3%), ANA and HLAB27 were positive among 33.3% and 12.5% of the studied cases, psoriasis in 33.3% of cases, Uveitis in 30.0%, uveitis complications were occurred in one patient. Biologic drugs were used in 25.0% of the patients. The study concludes that the characteristics of JPsA in Libyan children are different from those of other countries regarding a higher frequency of uveitis, equal sex-related distribution, and absence of nail changes. This difference may be attributed to different classification criteria used.

Introduction

The most common rheumatic disease among children is Juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA), which includes all arthritis forms that last for six weeks and onset before the age of 16 years [1]. Depending upon the geographical area, the incidence and prevalence vary between 1.6 to 23 for 100,000 children [2-9]. The categorization suggested by ILAR encompasses seven different, mutually exclusive classes, determined by clinical and laboratory measures [10]. Undifferentiated arthritis, not fit for criteria in any subtype, or fit for two or more subtypes [11]. Polyarticular JIA involves five or more joints during the first six months, occurs at any time before the age of 16 years [12, 13]. Systemic JIA (SJIA) is associated with a daily quotidian fever of 39°C persisting for more than two weeks. SJIA onset in adolescents is rare and adult onset is reported in a few cases [14]. Enthesitis-related arthritis (ERA) is arthritis and enthesitis of at least six weeks' duration [15]. The sacroiliacs, knees, ankles, and hips are the commonly affected joints at diagnosis, small joints of the feet and toes are involved [16]. Evidence for the heritability has shown that JIA has a sibling relative risk ranging from

15 to 30, similar to that of type 1 diabetes [17]. Although autoreactive B cells have other important pathogenic functions in JIA as antigen presenting cells within the synovium [18]. The pathetiologic role of infections in causing JIA, and the mediating role of genetic factors, remain unclear [19]. There are no laboratory test or combination of studies to confirm the diagnosis but they can be used to offer evidence of inflammation, support the clinical diagnosis [20].

Rheumatoid factor serology is shown to likely be positive in children with JIA and diseases other than JIA [21]. In individuals with oligoarticular onset disease, ANA deliberates risk for the development of asymptomatic uveitis [22]. Anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies can indicate severe patterns of disease, and not a diagnostic marker for JIA [23]. Magnetic Resonance Imaging is able to evaluate the manifestations of JIA [24]. Bone scans using technetium-99m are beneficial for detecting the early stage of inflammatory arthritis [25]. A multidisciplinary team approach to the management is important to improve the care of children with arthritis [26]. Intraarticular corticosteroid is effective treatment for synovitis with JIA [27, 28]. Methotrexate (MTX) is the usual first-line systemic immunosuppressive agent in children with JIA-associated uveitis, and in those who are refractory to, or dependent on topical glucocorticoids [29, 30]. Etanercept is used in JIA [31], which has been demonstrated to improve ability and quality of life [32, 33], and is potentially capable of reducing the progression of radiographic joint damage [34]. Infliximab with MTX has been shown to produce an important, rapid, and durable clinical effect with JIA [35]. Tocilizumab has proven useful even in patients whose JIA has been refractory and appears quite effective as monotherapy [36]. Systemic glucocorticoids are used for severe JIA-associated complications [37, 38]. Rapid and accurate diagnosis and therapy are essential to prevent permanent damage of the joint and preserve joint functionality [39].

The prevalence of psoriasis varies according to regions, but worldwide it is 2.0-11.0% [40]. The psoriasis location can increase the risk of psoriatic arthritis (PsA) with intergluteal and perianal lesions [41]. PsA is a differing inflammatory disorder marked by various clinical manifestations [42]. The American Rheumatism Association recognizes PsA as a separate disease [43]. Spondylitis presented in 40.0% [44]. The prevalence in Europe and other countries varies from 0.02 to 0.42% [45, 46]. There was a difference between PsA and psoriasis alone at three loci (*HLA-C*, *IL-12B* and *IL-23R*) [47]. Presence of two minor criteria is considered probable JPsA [48]. Two JPsA clinical subtypes are identified and is associated with HLA-B27; antinuclear antibodies are usually absent [49]. In PsA, especially the axial pattern, uveitis may initiate as unilateral and become bilateral in the course of the disease [50]. In peripheral arthritis, NSAID monotherapy without DMARDs should not exceed one, and other treatment possibilities should be considered. While when axial or enthesal involvement dominates the clinical picture, the duration of NSAID therapy might be prolonged up to 12 weeks, provided they have already induced relief for weeks [51]. Systemic glucocorticoids may be used with caution at the lowest effective dose, and MTX has proven efficacy in skin psoriasis and has become the standard DMARD for skin psoriasis [51]. Several other TNFi are approved in adult PsA for juvenile psoriasis; however, specific data on their effectiveness in JPsA remain scarce [52]. Despite this, identification and treatment are still not optimal, and the diagnosis was significantly delayed in the majority of patients. Delays in diagnoses of six and 12 months have been shown to impact long-term joint damage and functional disability [43]. Thus, the aim of this study was to determine all cases of psoriatic arthritis in terms of demographic data, diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis.

Materials and methods

Study design and period: This study was carried as cross-sectional study of the medical records of all the patients diagnosed with psoriatic arthritis who are referred to the Rheumatology Clinic.

Study setting: This study carried out in Tripoli Children's Hospital which is one of teaching hospital providing tertiary health care services, with a number of pediatric subspecialty clinic including: cardiology, endocrine, respiratory, neurology, gastroenterology, metabolic, neonatology, nephrology, and rheumatology clinic, the

rheumatology clinic is the only government clinic offer pediatric rheumatology services covering all western and south area of Libya.

Study population: The study was carried out by reviewing the medical records of children with a diagnosis of psoriatic arthritis according to the international League of Associations for Rheumatology Classification (ILAR) or Vancouver criteria (definite or probable). Patients with active disease as well as those in clinical remission were included in the period of 2001-2020.

Inclusion criteria: Any child diagnosed with psoriatic arthritis.

Exclusion criteria: Other types of juvenile idiopathic arthritis patients.

Study tool: A performed case sheet was used to obtain the relevant data from the medical records including the following: Age, sex, diagnosis, treatment and prognosis in the patients.

Study measurements: The following measurements were used in this study in the purpose of comparison: treatment regimens, disease activity which is represented by JADAS score in the form of inactive disease on treatment, active disease on treatment, inactive disease off treatment, active disease off treatment and disease outcome which was evaluated by JADI score.

Ethical consideration and consent process: Ethical approval was obtained from the scientific committee and the head of Tripoli Children's Hospital before starting the study.

Statistical analysis: The collected data was coded and SPSS software was used for analysis. Frequency, percentage, mean, and SD were used for descriptive statistics.

Results

In this study, out of 12 children meeting the Vancouver criteria for juvenile PsA, five cases (42.0%) did not fulfill ILAR criteria. Grounds for exclusion were family history of psoriasis limited to second-degree relatives (25.0%), presence of systemic JIA (8.3%), RF not done (8.3%) and HLA-B27 in a male with arthritis onset after age six (8.3%). In addition, JPsA represents 4.8% of total JIA cases.

Demographic data: Among the 12 patients, 50.0% were females, male: female ratio was 1: 1. The mean age of patients was 10.2 ± 6.5 years, disease onset above four years of age was observed in 50.0%, mean age of JPsA onset was 5.8 ± 5.3 years. 33.3% of the patients were diagnosed with psoriasis: Two had psoriasis before the onset of arthritis (median 10.0 months). Family history of psoriasis was found in 83.3% patients: 60.0% had a first-degree relative and 40.0% had a second-degree relative. One patient did not attend follow-up. The duration of follow up in the rest of the patients was 45.4%, less than two years, and 54.6% more than two years.

Clinical feature: Arthritis was presented in all cases; arthritis onset pattern is shown in **Table 1**. Polyarticular pattern was the predominant (58.3%). Hips were affected in one patient (8.3%), while no axial involvement, no nail changes were observed; dactylitis was observed in 66.7% of the cases. Enthesitis was seen in 8.3%. Systemic manifestations were observed in 8.3%. Uveitis was observed in 30.0% of cases, of which all were females, as shown in **Table 2**. Uveitis complications occurred in one, four-year-old-girl, who had psoriasis, early disease onset, ANA titer >1: 320 and negative HLAB27.

With regard to the serology result, rheumatoid factor, it was negative in all the patients. HLAB27 (missing values in four patients), it was positive in one patient (12.5%). The ANA was present in four patients accounting for 33.3%. ANA titer and pattern are shown in **Table 3**. ANA was more frequently seen in oligoarticular pattern (P=0.098), and the youngest age group at disease onset (P=0.221) Anti-CCP test (missing values in eight patients), negative in four patients.

Table 1: Comparison between arthritis patterns concerning JPsA general and clinical features

Variables	Polyarticular pattern N, (%)	Oligoarticular pattern N, (%)	P value
Gender			
Female	3 (42.9)	3 (60.0)	0.558
Male	4 (57.1)	2 (40.0)	
Age at disease onset			
≤ 4 yrs.	4 (57.1)	2 (40.0)	0.558
> 4yrs.	3 (42.9)	3 (60.0)	
Patients with psoriasis	3 (42.9)	1 (20.0)	0.408
Family history of psoriasis	5 (71.4)	5 (100)	0.190
Peripheral joints	7 (100)	5 (100)	
Axial joints	0.0 (0.0)	0.0 (0)	
Hip joints	1 (14.3)	0.0 (0)	0.377
Dactylitis	4 (57.1)	4 (80)	0.408
Enthesitis	1 (14.3)	0.0 (0)	0.377

Table 2: General characteristics and treatment of JPsA-associated uveitis

Variables	JPsA uveitis N, (%)	P value
Gender		
Female	3 (100)	0.038
Male	0 (0.0)	
Age at disease onset		
≤ 4 years	2 (66.7)	0.490
> 4 years	1 (33.3)	
Patients with psoriasis	2 (66.7)	0.098
Family history of psoriasis	2 (66.7)	0.571
Arthritis onset pattern		
Oligoarticular onset	2 (66.7)	0.260
Polyarticular onset	1 (33.3)	
Positive ANA	2 (66.7)	0.260
Positive HLAB27	0 (0.0)	0.408
Treatment		
NSAIDs	3 (100)	--
Methotrexate	3 (100)	0.301
Intra-articular injection	1 (33.3)	0.490
Biologics	2 (66.7)	0.098
Follow up duration		
≤ 2 years	0 (0.0)	0.161
> 2 years	3 (100)	

Table 3: ANA titer and pattern in JPsA children

ANA titer	JPsA patients N, (%) [ANA pattern]
> 1: 320	2 (16.7) [Mixed, homogenous]
1:160-320	2 (16.7) [Nucleolar, homogenous]
< 1: 80	8 (66.6)

With respect to the treatment, all JPsA were treated with NSAIDs at presentation and/or during follow-up. Methotrexate was used in 66.7% of the patients, as shown in **Table 4**; it was more frequently used in polyarticular than oligoarticular pattern disease (P=0.679). Biologics were used in 25.0% of the patients, were more used in females and in younger age patients at disease onset (P=0.083). Intra-articular injection was used in 16.7% of the patients. **Table 5** shows the disease outcome concerning clinical, laboratory data and treatment used.

Table 4: Medications used during the course of the disease

Treatment	Polyarticular pattern N, (%)	Oligoarticular pattern N, (%)	P value
NSAIDs	7 (100)	5 (100)	
Methotrexate	5 (71.4)	3 (60)	0.679
Intra-articular injection	1 (14.3)	1 (20)	0.793
Biologics	2 (28.6)	1 (20)	0.735

Table 5: Disease outcome concerning clinical, laboratory data, and treatment used

Variable	Articular damage only N, (%)	Both articular and extra- articular damage N, (%)	P value
Gender			
Female	1 (33.3)	1 (100)	0.248
Male	2 (66.7)	0 (0.0)	
Age at disease onset			
≤ 4 years	1 (33.3)	1 (100)	0.248
> 4 years	2 (66.7)	0 (0.0)	
Psoriasis in patient	0 (0.0)	1 (100)	0.046
Arthritis onset pattern			
Oligoarticular	1 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	0.505
Polyarticular	2 (66.7)	1 (100)	
Positive ANA	1 (33.3)	1 (100)	0.248
Positive HLAB27	1 (50) *	0 (0.0)	0.386
treatment regimens:			
NSAIDs & Methotrexate	2 (66.7)	1 (100)	0.505
NSAIDs, Methotrexate & biologics	0 (0.0)	1 (100)	0.083
Drug compliance			
Good	1 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	0.505
Poor	2 (66.7)	1 (100)	
Follow up duration			
≤ 2 years	2 (66.7)	0 (0)	0.248
> 2 years	1 (33.3)	1 (100)	

*One case is missing

Discussion

In the current study, medical records of 12 children at the Pediatric Rheumatology Clinic were retrospectively analyzed. This does not represent all cases seen in Libya during this period, but represents the referral pattern at Tripoli Children's Hospital. JPA was represents 4.8% of total JIA cases; it was 1.5% of JIA in Egyptian [53], 4.87% in the Saudi Arabia study [54], while in the Jordanian study, it was 8.5% [55]. There was no sex-related difference, on contrary to female predominance reported by Al-Hemair and others [54] and Stoll et al. [56]. Meanwhile, male predominance was reported by Alzyoud et al. [55] and Zisman et al. [57]. The mean age of disease onset was 5.8±5.3 year, which was lower than that reported in Canada (8.0±4.4 year) by Butbul et al [58] and by Al-Hemairi et al. [54] (8.47±3.09 years). The present results regarding psoriasis were higher than that reported by Stoll et al. [56], was 25.0%, but lower than that reported by Zisman et al. [57], who found psoriasis in 66.8% of the cases. Family history of psoriasis showed high frequency among patients as reported by Hamilton et al. [59] and Butbul et al. [58]. Similar to a previous study in Turkey by Kalyoncu et al. [60], polyarticular-onset was found to be the most common clinical pattern. In contrast to the results of Butbul et al. [58], who reported oligoarticular-onset predominance.

Concerning dactylitis, the current results were much higher than that reported by Butbul et al. [61] was 30.0%, while no nail changes were reported in the patients of this study, in contrast to 53.0% in the same study [61]. Being higher than the Saudi study [54], the frequency of ANA positivity in the children of the present study

was 33.3%, although a higher frequency was reported in Taiwan by Shen et al. [62] was 66.7%. Absence of ANA positivity was reported in other studies [9, 53, 55]. As found by Butbul et al. [60], it's more frequently seen in oligoarticular onset disease. HLAB27 was found in 12.5%, while higher results were reported by Flatøb et al. [63] by 19.0%. Previous studies in Taiwan [62] and America [56] reported by 33.3% and 46.0%, respectively. Uveitis was manifested among 33.3% of the cases, which was higher than that reported in Germany by 6.6% [64]. In contrast to the results of Abdwani et al. [9], Al-Hemairi et al. [54] and Hamilton et al. [59], who reported absent cases of uveitis. The present results were similar to the German study by Baquet-Walscheid [65] who found that JPsA-uveitis patients more frequently female, antinuclear antibody positive and younger at PsJA onset as well as in Libya [66]. As found by Butbul et al. [61], JPsA-uveitis occurred more occurred in oligoarticular onset disease. All patients in the current study were started on NSAIDs either alone or combined with DMARDs, but they were the only agent used in 33.3% of the patients [65]. In another study, NSAIDs were only used in combination with DMARDs [54]. MXT was used more in polyarticular onset disease, as reported in the other study [29].

Conclusions: This is the first study describing the pattern of juvenile psoriatic arthritis in Libyan children. The characteristics of JPsA in Libyan children are different from those of European, North American, and Arab countries regarding a higher frequency of uveitis, equal sex-related distribution, and absence of nail changes. This difference could be attributed to different classification criteria used.

References

1. Giancane G, Consolaro A, Lanni S, Davì S, Schiappapietra B, Ravelli A. Juvenil idiopathic arthritis: Diagnosis and treatment. *Rheumatology and Therapy*. 2016; 3(2): 187-207. doi: 10.1007/s40744-016-0040-4
2. Thatayatikom A, De Leucio A. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA). PubMed. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2020. Bookshelf ID: NBK554605. PMID: 32119492.
3. Berthold E, Månsson B, Kahn R. Outcome in juvenile idiopathic arthritis: A population-based study from Sweden. *Arthritis Research and Therapy*. 2019; 21(1): 218. doi: 10.1186/s13075-019-1994-8
4. Krause ML, Crowson CS, Michet CJ, Mason T, Muskardin TW, Matteson EL. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Olmsted County, Minnesota, 1960-2013. *Arthritis and Rheumatology*. 2016; 68(1): 247-254. doi: 10.1002/art.39323
5. Berntson L, Andersson Gäre B, Fasth A, Herlin T, Kristinsson J, Lahdenne P, et al. Incidence of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in the Nordic countries. A population-based study with special reference to the validity of the ILAR and EULAR criteria. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2003; 30(10): 2275-2282. doi: Nil.
6. Shiff NJ, Oen K, Kroeker K, Lix LM. Trends in population-based incidence and prevalence of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Manitoba, Canada. *Arthritis Care and Research*. 2019; 71(3): 413-418. doi: 10.1002/acr.23606
7. Modesto C, Antón J, Rodriguez B, Bou R, Arnal C, Ros J, et al. Incidence and prevalence of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Catalonia (Spain). *Scandinavian Journal of Rheumatology*. 2010; 39(6): 472-479. doi: 10.3109/03009741003742722
8. Danner S, Sordet C, Terzic J, Donato L, Velten M, Fischbach M, et al. Epidemiology of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Alsace, France. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2006; 33(7): 1377-1381. doi: Nil.
9. Abdwani R, Abdalla E, Al Arawi S, Al-Zakwani I. Epidemiology of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Oman. *Pediatric Rheumatology*. 2015; 13(1): 33. doi:10.1186/s12969-015-0030-z
10. Martini A, Ravelli A, Avcin T, Beresford MW, Burgos-Vargas R, Cuttica R, et al. Toward new classification criteria for juvenile idiopathic arthritis: First steps, Pediatric Rheumatology International Trials Organization International Consensus. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2018; 46(2):190-197. doi: 10.3899/jrheum.180168
11. Guzman J, Oen K, Tucker LB, Huber AM, Shiff N, Boire G, et al. The outcomes of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in children managed with contemporary treatments: results from the ReACCh-Out cohort. *Annals of the Rheumatic Disease*. 2015; 74(10): 1854-1860. doi: 10.1136/annrheumdis-2014-205372
12. Pires CF, Londe ACS, Pires AF, Pires LF, Almeida M do STM, Brito JJ da C, et al. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis: A study of 74 cases in Northeast Brazil. *Journal of Advanced Rheumatology Science*. 2017; 1(1): 8-18. doi: Nil.
13. Verbsky J, Oberle E, Harris J. Polyarticular juvenile idiopathic arthritis-epidemiology and management approaches. *Clinical Epidemiology*. 2014; 6: 379-393. doi: 10.2147/CLEP.S53168

14. Frosch M, Roth J. New insights in systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis-from pathophysiology to treatment. *Rheumatology*. 2008; 47(2): 121-125. doi: 10.1093/rheumatology/kem271
15. Weiss P. Diagnosis and treatment of enthesitis-related arthritis. *Adolescent Health, Medicine and Therapeutics*. 2012; 3: 67-74. doi: 10.2147/AHMT.S25872
16. Weiss PF, Klink AJ, Behrens EM, Sherry DD, Finkel TH, Feudtner C, et al. Enthesitis in an inception cohort of enthesitis-related arthritis. *Arthritis Care and Research*. 2011; 63(9): 1307-1312. doi: 10.1002/acr.20508
17. Cobb JE, Hinks A, Thomson W. The genetics of juvenile idiopathic arthritis: current understanding and future prospects. *Rheumatology*. 2013; 53(4): 592-599. doi: 10.1093/rheumatology/ket314
18. Mahmud SA, Binstadt BA. Autoantibodies in the pathogenesis, diagnosis, and prognosis of juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 2019; 9: 3168. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2018.03168
19. Horton DB, Shenoi S. Review of environmental factors and juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Open Access Rheumatology: Research and Reviews*. 2019; 11: 253-267. doi: 10.2147/OARRR.S165916
20. Kim KH, Kim DS. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis: Diagnosis and differential diagnosis. *Korean Journal of Pediatrics*. 2010; 53(11): 931-935. doi: 10.3345/kjp.2010.53.11.931
21. Eichenfield AH, Athreya BH, Doughty RA, Cebul RD. Utility of rheumatoid factor in the diagnosis of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. *Pediatrics*. 1986; 78(3): 480-484. PMID: 3748683.
22. Petty RE, Smith JR, Rosenbaum JT. Arthritis and uveitis in children: A pediatric rheumatology perspective. *American Journal of Ophthalmology*. 2003; 135(6): 879-884. doi: 10.1016/s0002-9394(03)00104-1
23. Kuna AT, Lamot L, Miler M, Harjacek M, Simundic A-M, Vrkic N. Antibodies to mutated citrullinated vimentin and antibodies to cyclic citrullinated peptides in juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine*. 2009; 47(12): 1525-1530. doi:10.1515/CCLM.2009.288
24. Lamer S, Sebag GH. MRI and ultrasound in children with juvenile chronic arthritis. *European Journal of Radiology*. 2000; 33(2): 85-93. doi: 10.1016/s0720-048x(99)00158-8
25. Qing C, Lei Y, Ma L, Xie P, Deng H. [A clinical study on the diagnosis of early rheumatoid arthritis using bone imaging with ^{99m}Tc-MDP]. *Sheng Wu Yi Xue Gong Cheng Xue Za Zhi = Journal of Biomedical Engineering = Shengwu Yixue Gongchengxue Zazhi*. 2008; 25(5): 1193-1196. PMID: 19024474
26. Ruth NM, Passo MH. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis: management and therapeutic options. *Therapeutic Advances in Musculoskeletal Disease*. 2011; 4(2): 99-110. doi:10.1177/1759720X11413630
27. Scott C, Meiorin S, Filocamo G, Lanni S, Valle M, Martinoli C, et al. A reappraisal of intra-articular corticosteroid therapy in juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Clinical and Experimental Rheumatology*. 2010; 28(5): 774-781. PMID: 20863449.
28. Elkheshbi AH, Alaeb KAA, Almarafy MJ. Comparative effects of intra-articular hyaluronic acid and corticosteroids combined with physiotherapy on knee osteoarthritis: A quantitative study at Mitiga Military Hospital. *Mediterranean Journal of Medical Research*. 2025; 2: 120-128. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.1689885
29. Ravelli A, Martini A. Methotrexate in juvenile idiopathic arthritis: answers and questions. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2000; 27(8): 1830-1833. PMID: 10955319.
30. Angeles-Han ST, Ringold S, Beukelman T, Lovell D, Garcia CAC, Becker ML, et al. 2018 American College of Rheumatology/Arthritis Foundation Guideline for the Screening, Monitoring, and Treatment of Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis-Associated Uveitis. *Arthritis and rheumatology*. 2019; 71(6): 864-877. doi: 10.1002/art.40885
31. Lovell DJ, Giannini EH, Reiff A, Cawkwell GD, Silverman ED, Nocton JJ, et al. Etanercept in children with polyarticular juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. *Pediatric Rheumatology Collaborative Study Group*. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 2000; 342(11): 763-769. doi: 10.1056/NEJM200003163421103
32. Prince FHM, Geerdink LM, Borsboom GJJM, Twilt M, van Rossum MJ, Hoppenreijns EPH, et al. Major improvements in health-related quality of life during the use of etanercept in patients with previously refractory juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*. 2010; 69(1): 138-142. doi: 10.1136/ard.2009.111260
33. Giannini EH, Ilowite NT, Lovell DJ, Wallace CA, Rabinovich CE, Reiff A, et al. Effects of long-term etanercept treatment on growth in children with selected categories of juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Arthritis and Rheumatism*. 2010; 62(11): 3259-3264. doi: 10.1002/art.27682
34. Nielsen S, Ruperto N, Gerloni V, Simonini G, Cortis E, Lepore L, et al. Preliminary evidence that etanercept may reduce radiographic progression in juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Clinical and Experimental Rheumatology*. 2008; 26(4): 688-692. PMID: 18799107.
35. Kim KN. Treatment of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. *Korean Journal of Pediatrics*. 2010; 53(11): 936-941. doi: 10.3345/kjp.2010.53.11.936
36. Turnier JL, Brunner HI. Tocilizumab for treating juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Expert Opinion on Biological Therapy*. 2016; 16(4): 559-566. doi: 10.1517/14712598.2016.1150997
37. Batu ED. Glucocorticoid treatment in juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Rheumatology International*. 2019; 39(1): 13-27. doi: 10.1007/s00296-018-4168-0

38. Clarke SLN, Sen ES, Ramanan AV. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis-associated uveitis. *Pediatric Rheumatology*. 2016; 14(1): 27. doi: 10.1186/s12969-016-0088-2
39. Zierhut M, Deuter C, Murray PI. Classification of uveitis - current guidelines. *European Ophthalmic Review*. 2007; 00(00): 77. doi: 10.17925/EOR.2007.00.00.77
40. Malattia C, Rinaldi M, Martini A. The role of imaging in juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *Expert Review of Clinical Immunology*. 2018; 14(8): 681-694. doi: 10.1080/1744666X.2018.1496019
41. Rendon A, Schäkel K. Psoriasis Pathogenesis and Treatment. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2019; 20(6): 1475. doi: 10.3390/ijms20061475
42. Vanessa Ocampo D, Gladman D. Psoriatic arthritis. *f1000research*. 2019; 8: 1665. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.19144.1
43. Belasco J, Wei N. Psoriatic Arthritis: What is Happening at the Joint?. *Rheumatology and Therapy*. 2019; 6(3) 305-315. doi: 10.1007/s40744-019-0159-1
44. Coates LC, Helliwell PS. Psoriatic arthritis: state of the art review. *Clinical Medicine*. 2017; 17(1): 65-70. doi: 10.7861/clinmedicine.17-1-65
45. Gladman DD. Psoriatic arthritis: epidemiology, clinical features, course, and outcome. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*. 2005; 64(suppl_2): ii14-ii17. doi: 10.1136/ard.2004.032482
46. Liu JT, Yeh HM, Liu SY, Chen KT. Psoriatic arthritis: Epidemiology, diagnosis, and treatment. *World Journal of Orthopedics*. 2014; 5(4): 537-543. doi: 10.5312/wjo.v5.i4.537
47. Bedaiwi M, Al-Homood IA, El-Garf A, Uthman I, Sunna N, Nassier R, et al. Disease burden and treatment challenges of psoriatic arthritis in Africa and the Middle East. *Rheumatology International*. 2019; 39(8): 1321-1329. doi: 10.1007/s00296-019-04319-3
48. Szczerkowska-Dobosz A, Krasowska D, Bartosińska J, Stawczyk-Macieja M, Walczak A, Owczarczyk-Saczonek A, et al. Pathogenesis of psoriasis in the “omic” era. Part IV. Epidemiology, genetics, immunopathogenesis, clinical manifestation and treatment of psoriatic arthritis. *Advances in Dermatology and Allergology/Postępy Dermatologii i Alergologii*. 2020; 37(5): 625-634. doi: 10.5114/ada.2020.100478
49. Ogdie A, Weiss P. The Epidemiology of Psoriatic Arthritis. *Rheumatic Disease Clinics of North America*. 2015; 41(4): 545-568. doi: 10.1016/j.rdc.2015.07.001
50. Ritchlin CT, Colbert RA, Gladman DD. Psoriatic Arthritis. *The New England journal of medicine*. 2017; 376(10): 957-970. doi: 10.1056/NEJMra1505557
51. Fotiadou C, Lazaridou E. Psoriasis and uveitis: links and risks. *Psoriasis: Targets and Therapy*. 2019; 9: 91-96. doi: 10.2147/PTT.S179182
52. Gossec L, Smolen JS, Ramiro S, de Wit M, Cutolo M, Dougados M, et al. European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) recommendations for the management of psoriatic arthritis with pharmacological therapies: 2015 update. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*. 2016; 75(3): 499-510. doi: 10.1136/annrheumdis-2015-208337
53. Brunello F, Tirelli F, Pegoraro L, Dell’Apa F, Alfisi A, Calzamatta G, et al. New Insights on Juvenile Psoriatic Arthritis. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2022; 10: 884727. doi: 10.3389/fped.2022.884727
54. Almalky MA-E, Rasheed EM, Mortada MA, Ayyad KM. Different patterns of juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Zagazig University Hospitals, Mohamed Abd-Elkader Almalky, Ehab Mahmoud Rasheed. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2021; 85(1): 2925-2929. doi: 10.21608/ejhm.2021.191393
55. Al-Hemairi MH, Albokhari SM, Muzaffer MA. The Pattern of Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis in a Single Tertiary Center in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Inflammation*. 2016; 2016(1): 7802957. doi: 10.1155/2016/7802957
56. Alzyoud RM, Alsuweiti MO, Almaaitah HQ, Aladaileh BN, Alnoubani MK, Alwahadneh AM. Juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Jordan: single center experience. *Pediatric Rheumatology Online Journal*. 2021; 19(1): 90. doi: 10.1186/s12969-021-00572-8
57. Stoll ML, Zurakowski D, Nigrovic LE, Nichols DP, Sundel RP, Nigrovic PA. Patients with juvenile psoriatic arthritis comprise two distinct populations. *Arthritis and Rheumatism*. 2006; 54 (11): 3564-3572. doi: 10.1002/art.22173
58. Zisman D, Gladman DD, Stoll ML, Strand V, Lavi I, Hsu JJ, et al. The juvenile psoriatic arthritis cohort in the CARRA registry: Clinical characteristics, classification, and outcomes. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2017; 44(3): 342-251. doi: 10.3899/jrheum.160717
59. Butbul Aviel Y, Tyrrell P, Schneider R, Dhillon S, Feldman BM, Laxer R, et al. Juvenile psoriatic arthritis (JPsA): Juvenile arthritis with psoriasis? *Pediatric Rheumatology*. 2013; 11(1): 11. doi: 10.1186/1546-0096-11
60. Hamilton ML, Gladman DD, Shore A, Laxer RM, Silverman ED. Juvenile psoriatic arthritis and HLA antigens. *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*. 1990; 49(9): 694-697. doi: 10.1136/ard.49.9.694
61. Kalyoncu U, Bayindir Ö, Ferhat Öksüz M, Doğru A, Kimyon G, Tarhan EF, et al. The psoriatic arthritis registry of Turkey: Results of a multicenter registry on 1081 patients. *Rheumatology*. 2017; 56(2): 279-286. doi: 10.1093/rheumatology/kew375

62. Butbul YA, Tyrrell PN, Schneider R, Dhillon S, Feldman BM, Laxer RM, et al. Comparison of Patients with Juvenile Psoriatic Arthritis and Nonpsoriatic Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis: How Different Are They?. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2009; 36(9): 2033-2041. doi: 10.3899/jrheum.080674
63. Shen C-C, Yeh K-W, Ou L-S, Yao T-C, Chen L-C, Huang J-L. Clinical features of children with juvenile idiopathic arthritis using the ILAR classification criteria: A community-based cohort study in Taiwan. *Journal of Microbiology, Immunology and Infection*. 2013; 46(4): 288-294. doi: 10.1016/j.jmii.2012.03.006
64. Flatø B, Lien G, Smerdel-Ramoya A, Vinje O. Juvenile psoriatic arthritis: longterm outcome and differentiation from other subtypes of juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2009; 36(3): 642-650. doi: 10.3899/jrheum.080543
65. Baquet-Walscheid K, Rothaus K, Niewerth M, Klotsche J, Minden K, Heiligenhaus A. Occurrence and risk factors of uveitis in juvenile psoriatic arthritis: Data from a population-based nationwide study in Germany. *The Journal of Rheumatology*. 2022; 49(7): 719-724. doi: 10.3899/jrheum.210755
66. Hashad SS, Etayari HM, Altwati AA. Anakinra treatment for systemic onset juvenile idiopathic arthritis in Libyan Children. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2025; 5(4): 38-46. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17553885

Author contribution: Both authors contributed equally, approved the final version of the manuscript, and agreed to be accountable for its contents.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Ethical issues: The authors completely observed ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, data fabrication or falsification, and double publication or submission.

Data availability statement: The raw data that support the findings of this article are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Author declarations: The authors confirm that they have followed all relevant ethical guidelines and obtained any necessary IRB and/or ethics committee approvals.

Generative AI disclosure: No generative AI was used in the preparation of this manuscript.